

Statement on Temporary Stewardship of the mzPeak Trademark

Background

mzPeak is being developed as a next-generation, open, scalable, and community-driven mass spectrometry data format intended to support long-term accessibility, interoperability, and broad adoption across the mass spectrometry field. The mzPeak white paper presents it as an open effort involving researchers, vendors, software developers, and regulators, with strong emphasis on open implementation and broad collaboration [1].

As technical development progresses, the mzPeak name may become increasingly important as the identifier of the format, its specification, and its implementations. To reduce the risk that an unrelated third party takes control of the mzPeak name through trademark registration, the undersigned wish to set out the principles under which such a trademark, if pursued, should be registered, held, and governed.

Purpose

This document records the current public commitment of the undersigned participants in the mzPeak effort regarding the temporary stewardship of the mzPeak trademark. It reflects the shared understanding reached during consortium discussions on this topic.

Its purpose is to provide transparency to the mzPeak community and external stakeholders on the governance principles under which the trademark would be held and, in due course, transferred to an independent nonprofit or other appropriate legal entity.

Statement

The trademark should be registered solely as a defensive measure to prevent third parties from taking control of the mzPeak name, not to give OpenMS Inc., as a company, long-term control over the standard. If OpenMS files the trademark, this should therefore be clearly presented as a temporary custodial role until a corporate mzPeak consortium, or an independent nonprofit or other appropriate legal entity, is established. There should also be an explicit commitment that ownership of the trademark will be transferred free of charge once such a body exists. In the meantime, trademark ownership must not restrict access to the mzPeak specification, contributions to its development, or implementation by others.

Because mzPeak is a multi-stakeholder effort, decisions about trademark use, compatibility, and eventual transfer should involve broader input from the mzPeak consortium and its stakeholders. It should also be made clear that the trademark is not intended to give OpenMS leverage over vendors, competing implementations, or commercial adoption. In practice, this means it should not allow OpenMS to decide which vendors may participate, to slow down competing implementations (like vendor formats), or to use the trademark as pressure against the vendors. This is important not only in substance, but also in perception: even if the intention is purely defensive, holding the trademark in the name of one company may raise concerns among vendors (and other partners). For that reason, both the safeguards and the communication around them matter. If this approach is pursued, the rationale should be communicated early and clearly to all involved parties, including the vendors, to avoid unnecessary distrust or the impression of unilateral control.

Practical interpretation

The undersigned understand the above statement to imply the following:

1. OpenMS may act as a temporary filing and holding party for the mzPeak trademark, solely for defensive purposes.
2. OpenMS does not, by virtue of such temporary stewardship, acquire long-term governance control over mzPeak as a standard.
3. The mzPeak specification, its development, and its implementation remain open to broader participation.
4. Any future rules regarding use of the mzPeak name, compatibility claims, or transfer of the trademark should be discussed with the current open mzPeak consortium.
5. Once an independent nonprofit or other appropriate legal entity exists that is suitable to hold the trademark on behalf of the broader mzPeak effort, OpenMS is expected to transfer ownership free of charge.
6. The trademark must not be used to restrict participation by vendors, discourage alternative implementations, or distort commercial adoption.

Public availability

This statement is intended to be made publicly available to ensure transparency for contributors, vendors, and other stakeholders.

Endorsement and publication

The current version of this statement is endorsed by:

- **Samuel P. Wein**, representing OpenMS Inc. as temporary filing and holding party if the trademark is pursued, and last author of the mzPeak white paper
- **Tim Van Den Bossche**, lead author of the mzPeak white paper and mzPeak consortium representative
- **Joshua Klein**, lead technical developer and mzPeak consortium representative

Versioning

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A publicly archived version of this statement may be made available through Zenodo and referenced from the mzPeak GitHub repository.

References

[1] Van Den Bossche T, Alexandrov T, Bilbao A, et al. *mzPeak: Designing a Scalable, Interoperable, and Future-Ready Mass Spectrometry Data Format*. *Journal of Proteome Research*. 2025;24:5329-5335. doi:10.1021/acs.jproteome.5c00435.